

Recent trends in chemical sciences^ψ

Suresh C. Ameta

President, Indian Chemical Society

Science is the forerunner of new ideas and fresh concepts. In the last century, we have had new discoveries that could expand options for the energy system such as photoelectric effect, which provides the basis for photovoltaic technology, nuclear reactions that gave us power; superconductivity, which has the potential to advance energy aspect of the power system, i.e. generation, transmission and so on.

The need of the new millenium seems to be microscale experiments in chemistry. Disposal of products, use of excess reagents and solvents pose a threat to the environment and hence the health hazards in laboratories to the students, teachers and other laboratory staff have been a matter of concern to many of us for a long time. A tug of war had also been going on in recent years to balance the budget of running practical classes and yet maintaining high standards of training. Since the economy is always the winner and deciding factor, some of the experiments have become only show-pieces or decorative parts of the syllabi and hence, there is a pressing demand to go for microscale experiments in the future from economic as well as pollution point of view.

The experimental discovery of fullerene about a decade-and-a-half back has thrown a world of hollow 3D molecules formed by carbon atoms only. Alkali metal derivatives of C₆₀ are superconducting in behavior. In addition to this, making of molecular traps, molecular ferromagnets and molecular bearings will become feasible and the future for the chemistry of fullerenes and fulleroids seems to be quite bright. The electrosynthetic and electroanalytical aspects of this black diamond will occupy a position near the heart of fullerene chemistry. The mechanism of fullerene growth, its interconversion and finally chemical reactivity promises to provide a fertile field for researchers in years to come. There remain much more facts still unexplored about fullerenes.

Anandamide, a brain constituent that functions as a natural ligand to the cannabinoid receptors is the molecule of the year. Recently, it has been discovered that it is possible to generate the photosensitizer inside the tumor by the typical or even oral applications of the so-called 'pre-photosensitizer'. In addition to this, hybrid molecules, in

which a photosensitizer is covalently linked to a chemotherapeutic drug, are being developed as combination therapy (chemo + photo) against cancer. Photodynamic therapy (PDT) is a newly emerging technique in combating with cancer where a photosensitizing molecule acts against malignant tumors in presence of light. Singlet oxygen plays an important role in this process. A new breed of porphyrins is being explored for combination therapy against cancer. Thus, in a very short period, photodynamic therapy has progressed from cardiology, ophthalmology and dermatology to oncology.

The pioneering work on conducting polymers has paved way for conjugated organic systems towards photonic and electronic applications. An insulating polymer can be made conducting to the extent of metallic state. These conjugated polymers are likely to play an important role in the fabrication of molecular electronic circuits; thus reducing the dimensions of the electronic circuits from 200 nm to 1 nm. This reduction in size of the circuit may bring a revolution in the field of computer, where the speed and dynamic memory of computers can be increased to the order of 10⁶ times.

Some organometallic compounds of 4d-transition metals can be easily prepared by microwave chemistry, which are often impossible to prepare by conventional methods. Other major applications of microwave chemistry are hydrolysis of peptides and proteins, waste water treatment, drug release, polymer chemistry, etc.

Microwave heating has been found a very convenient thermal source not only in kitchen but also in a chemical laboratory. There has been an exponential growth in this field in the last decade. Microwave chemistry has been considered as an asset to develop such green chemical pathways and it has been used from kitchen to the laboratory. These microwave-mediated organic reactions are fast, safe and are eco-friendly with a good yield. In a number of cases, these reactions are carried out even in dry-media on solid support.

Microwave has provided a way to eco-friendly methods leading to the development of green chemistry. It has a number of applications, the worthmentioning are waste

^ψPresidential Address delivered at 37th. Annual Convention of Chemists held at Hardwar, on November 15, 2000

treatment, polymer technology, drug release or targeting, ceramics, etc. It will simplify time-consuming conventional procedures and it is hoped that appropriate technology will be developed so that some of the fascinating microwave assisted transformations could be done on industrial scales, thereby, increasing the overall efficiency of the process and reducing pollutions of the environment through the use of solvent-free reaction protocols.

In the last two decades, local environmental concerns became important issues in making choices. To this, one adds global environmental concern that calls for reduction in use of fossil fuels to reduce green house gases so as to mitigate climate changes. Here the photoreduction of carbon dioxide enters the scene. It is indeed unfortunate that even in the beginning of 21st century, millions of women in rural areas are spending hours together gathering bio-

fuels travelling many kilometers and carrying them, suffering health effects due to smoke arising in the process of use of bio-fuels and exposing their children to these ill-effects.

The term 'Green Chemistry' has been coined at Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) and it represents the chemical processes, where environmental pollutants can be replaced by less polluting or non-polluting alternatives. It involves designing newer chemical synthesis and products, which protect our clean environment. This green chemistry wave has recently reached India and there is a pressing need for all of us to work for its betterment by developing newer green chemical routes and it is all equally important to develop a collaboration between academics and industrialists to have an immediate transfer of these green products to the market.